

Cultural Competence of College Student on Indigenous Cultural Communities in Bukidnon

Kenneth D. Secretaria ^{1a} Evan P. Taja-on, MSc ^{2b}

¹School of Arts and Science, San Isidro College, Malaybalay City, Bukidnon, 8700

²School of Education, San Isidro College, Malaybalay City, Bukidnon, 8700

✉ ^aksecretaria@sic.edu.ph, ^betajaon@sic.edu.ph

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ABSTRACT

Cultural competence refers to the ability to effectively understand, appreciate, and respect cultural differences and nuances. It is becoming increasingly important in today's diverse society for college students to develop cultural competence to effectively interact with people from different backgrounds and cultures. The study aims to identify the gaps in cultural competence among college students taking up the subject course Reading in Philippine History with Indigenous People Studies, identify areas for improvement, and provide recommendations. The study utilized a descriptive research design using simple random sampling to identify the respondents. Moreover, the study used an adapted research questionnaire and employed a first-year college student taking up the subject course Readings in Philippine History with Indigenous People Studies during the second semester of the academic year 2022-2023. Based on the results of the study, the students have an average level of personal involvement, skills in culture, and knowledge of culture regarding the Cultural Communities in Bukidnon. On the other hand, the students have a high level of awareness of the culture of the Indigenous Cultural Communities in Bukidnon. Overall, the students have an average level of cultural competence. The students have a generally positive level of interest, involvement, and knowledge about the Indigenous Cultural Communities in Bukidnon and their culture.

Keywords: *Indigenous People, Cultural Awareness, Cultural Competence, Indigenous Cultural Communities*

INTRODUCTION

BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

The Philippine culture primarily comprises of Filipino and Spanish Catholic traditions with some influences from other Asian countries and America. With the progress of modernization, some cultures are being forgotten like traditional games, courtship, clothing, and folk beliefs

(Tongco, 2019). Some courses are treating cultures and traditions as ‘gap fillers’ in textbooks and classes and only treating the content as a ‘need to complete the course’ (Torres, 2016). According to the article of Ty (2010), the indigenous people of the Mindanao expressed that they have problems of non-representation of all levels of education and discrimination. Moreover, the indigenous communities struggle with their right to independence and to their ancestral domains. Which further the gap of knowledge and understanding regarding the indigenous communities of Bukidnon.

The course Readings in the Philippine History with Indigenous People’s Studies encourages the students to explore the diverse history of, not only of the nation, but also with the locality. Mindanao comprises 66% of the indigenous people of the Philippines (Ty, 2010). Bukidnon is rich with diverse culture with seven (7) indigenous tribes, namely the Bukidnon, Higa-onon, Manobo, Matigsalug, Talaandig, Tigwahanon, and Umayamnon (Provincial Government of Bukidnon, 2012). The course encourages the students to connect and understand the different indigenous communities that are present in the locality. The course pushes the students to go beyond the books and associate themselves with the lives and culture of the indigenous communities.

The course Readings in the Philippine History with Indigenous People’s Studies aim to provide learners with an avenue for learners to explore the different communities of the locality along with some traditional practices and beliefs (Tharp, 2017; Grosser, 2020). The objective of the study seeks to assess the students’ competence regarding the indigenous cultural communities of Bukidnon before and after course as a basis for improving instruction. Correspondingly, cultural competence refers to the ability to understand, appreciate, and effectively interact with people from diverse cultural backgrounds (Guzman, et al., 2016). Cultural competence, in the context of this study, has five (5) main components: Knowledge on cultural communities, which is the understanding of different cultural values, beliefs, and practices; Personal involvement is the active participation in cultural activities and experiences; Awareness of cultures is the ability to recognize and acknowledge one's own cultural biases and values; Knowledge on culture is the willingness and openness to learn from and embrace cultural differences; And skills on culture, which is the ability to effectively communicate and interact with people from diverse cultural backgrounds (Mason, 1995; Great Vancouver Island Multicultural Society, 2017).

This research topic aims to examine the cultural competence of college students towards the indigenous cultural communities of Bukidnon. The study will employ the lens of Philippine history and indigenous studies to understand how the historical and cultural context has influenced the students' perceptions and attitudes towards the Bukidnon indigenous community. The research seeks to determine the cultural competence among college students regarding the indigenous cultural communities of the Bukidnon. The study sought to assess the first-year college students taking the course Reading in the Philippine History with Indigenous People’s Studies during the second semester of the Academic Year 2022-2023 at San Isidro College.

Theoretical Framework

The study anchors on the concept developed by Dinges (1983) on intercultural competence. Intercultural competence refers to the ability to interact effectively and appropriately with people from diverse cultures. It involves understanding and respect for cultural differences, developing skills to communicate across cultures, and adapting to unfamiliar cultural environments (Leung,

Ang, & Tan, 2014; Arasaratnam, 2016). In the case of the study, using intercultural competence as a theoretical framework will enable researchers to explore the extent to which students possess the skills and knowledge necessary to engage with the Bukidnon community respectfully and effectively. Moreover, it will help in identifying the strategies and interventions that can be implemented to enhance intercultural competence among college students.

The conceptual framework of the study as depicted in Figure 1 illustrates the framework of the study. The independent variable is the student’s cultural awareness of the indigenous communities of Bukidnon which will be associated with the student’s cultural competence.

Figure 1.
Framework of the Study

Cultural competence refers to the ability to effectively interact with and understand individuals from different cultural backgrounds. It involves having knowledge and understanding of different cultural practices, beliefs, and values and the ability to communicate and interact with individuals from these backgrounds in a respectful and appropriate manner (Guzman, et al., 2016). For college students, cultural competence is especially important as they encounter individuals from diverse backgrounds on campus and in their future careers. This includes interactions with classmates, professors, and individuals in the community (Grosser, 2020).

The theory of intercultural competence emphasizes the importance of developing knowledge, skills, and attitudes that allow individuals to effectively navigate intercultural interactions. This includes understanding one's own cultural biases and assumptions, adapting communication styles to fit different cultural contexts, and developing the ability to empathize and understand different perspectives (Savicki, 2020). In college, developing cultural competence can be facilitated through diversity and inclusion initiatives, cultural exchange programs, and multicultural education in the curriculum. By developing cultural competence, college students can become better prepared for success in a globalized and diverse world (Tharp, 2017).

Students’ cultural competence of Mason (1995) has two components and the Greater Vancouver Island Multicultural Society (2017) has three components. The study has five (5) main components. The first component on *knowledge of community* evaluates the students’ awareness of the indigenous communities of Bukidnon. The second component is on *personal involvement* that assesses the student’s participation and contribution on the indigenous communities. The third component is on *awareness of culture* which measures the student’s familiarity on the different indigenous community present in Bukidnon. The fourth component is on *knowledge of culture* which measures the students understanding regarding the different indigenous communities of Bukidnon. And the last component is on *skills on culture* which evaluates the student’s ability on develop understanding on the different indigenous culture.

Statement of the Problem

The main goal of the study was to assess the students' cultural competence on the Indigenous Cultural Communities in Bukidnon. Specifically, the study aims to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of cultural competence of the student in terms of:
 - 1.1. knowledge of communities;
 - 1.2. personal involvement;
 - 1.3. awareness of culture;
 - 1.4. knowledge of culture; and
 - 1.5. skills on culture?
2. Is there a significant difference between the components of the student's cultural competence?

METHODOLOGY

The study utilized the descriptive research design. The researchers collected data on the cultural competence of the student taking up Reading in Philippine History with Indigenous People Studies. The study used simple random sampling in gathering data. The participant of the study were the first-year college students of the second semester of the Academic Year 2022-2023. Data will be gathered from the different schools under the college department of San Isidro College. The study has a total of 102 respondents.

The study adapted the instrument developed by Mason (1995) and modified the questions to suit the need of the study in gathering data. The study adapted two major components, namely, the first component, *knowledge of communities* with nineteen (19) statements reflecting students' knowledge on the indigenous people in the Bukidnon. Using a 4-point scale with a Cronbach alpha of 0.718, the criteria used the following:

<u>Scale</u>	<u>Range</u>	<u>Quantitative Description</u>	<u>Qualitative Interpretation</u>
4	3.26–4.00	Very Well / Always	High Knowledge on Cultural Communities
3	2.51–3.25	Fairly Well / Fairly Often	Average Knowledge on Cultural Communities
2	1.76–2.50	Barely / Sometimes / Occasionally	Low Knowledge on Cultural Communities
1	1.00–1.75	Not at All / Never	Limited Knowledge on Cultural Communities

The second component is *personal involvement* with eight (8) statements reflecting the students' interaction and immersion to the indigenous communities. Using a 4-point scale with a Cronbach alpha of 0.824, the criteria used the following:

<u>Scale</u>	<u>Range</u>	<u>Quantitative Description</u>	<u>Qualitative Interpretation</u>
4	3.26–4.00	Very Well / Always	High Personal Involvement
3	2.51–3.25	Fairly Well / Fairly Often	Average Personal Involvement
2	1.76–2.50	Barely / Sometimes / Occasionally	Low Personal Involvement
1	1.00–1.75	Not at All / Never	Limited Personal Involvement

Together with the instrument developed by the Greater Vancouver Island Multicultural Society (2017) containing three (3) major components, namely, and the third component is *awareness of culture* with eleven (11) statements that assess the students' mindfulness of the culture in the locality. Using a 4-point scale with a Cronbach alpha of 0.811, the criteria used the following:

<u>Scale</u>	<u>Range</u>	<u>Quantitative Description</u>	<u>Qualitative Interpretation</u>
4	3.26–4.00	Very Well / Always	High Awareness on Culture
3	2.51–3.25	Fairly Well / Fairly Often	Average Awareness on Culture
2	1.76–2.50	Barely / Sometimes / Occasionally	Low Awareness on Culture
1	1.00–1.75	Not at All / Never	Limited Awareness on Culture

The fourth component is *knowledge of culture* with twelve (12) statements that assess the students' sense about the local culture. Using a 4-point scale with a Cronbach alpha of 0.751, the criteria used the following:

<u>Scale</u>	<u>Range</u>	<u>Quantitative Description</u>	<u>Qualitative Interpretation</u>
4	3.26–4.00	Very Well / Always	High Knowledge on Culture
3	2.51–3.25	Fairly Well / Fairly Often	Average Knowledge on Culture
2	1.76–2.50	Barely / Sometimes / Occasionally	Low Knowledge on Culture
1	1.00–1.75	Not at All / Never	Limited Knowledge on Culture

And the last component is *skill on culture* with twelve (12) statements that assess the students' capacity to adapt and learn with the culture of the locality. Using a 4-point scale with a Cronbach alpha of 0.792, the criteria used the following:

<u>Scale</u>	<u>Range</u>	<u>Quantitative Description</u>	<u>Qualitative Interpretation</u>
4	3.26–4.00	Very Well / Always	High Skill on Culture
3	2.51–3.25	Fairly Well / Fairly Often	Average Skill on Culture
2	1.76–2.50	Barely / Sometimes / Occasionally	Low Skill on Culture
1	1.00–1.75	Not at All / Never	Limited Skill on Culture

The questionnaire assesses the student's cultural competence and identify the student strengths and areas for development. Overall, a 4-point scale evaluates the student's cultural competence and has a Cronbach-alpha of 0.809. The criteria used the following:

<u>Scale</u>	<u>Range</u>	<u>Quantitative Description</u>	<u>Qualitative Interpretation</u>
4	3.26–4.00	Very Well / Always	High Cultural Competence
3	2.51–3.25	Fairly Well / Fairly Often	Average Cultural Competence
2	1.76–2.50	Barely / Sometimes / Occasionally	Low Cultural Competence
1	1.00–1.75	Not at All / Never	Limited Cultural Competence

All data will be treated using descriptive statistics and ANOVA to compare the five components of cultural competence of the learners. The researchers implemented the provision of the Data Privacy Act of 2012 in the data gathering procedure. The participants were asked to sign a written consent form giving their permission to gather data from them.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The study examined the cultural competence of the college students taking up Reading in Philippine History with Indigenous People Study. Data gathering from the respondents was through survey method. The study used descriptive statistics and ANOVA to treat the quantitative data of the study.

Students Level of Cultural Competence in term of the Components

Table 1 displays the students' level of cultural competence in terms of the five (5) components. Additionally, Table 1 displays the mean score, standard deviation, and qualitative interpretation of the student's cultural competence. Furthermore, Table 1 presents the mean score and qualitative interpretation of the cultural competence of the students.

Table 1.

Students mean score on the five components of cultural competence

Components	Mean	S.D.	Q.I.
Personal Involvement	2.57	0.597	Average Personal Involvement
Skills on Culture	3.03	0.626	Average Skills on Culture
Knowledge on Culture	3.07	0.582	Average Knowledge on Culture
Knowledge of Cultural Communities	3.10	0.539	Average Knowledge on Cultural Communities
Awareness of Culture	3.31	0.606	High Awareness on Culture
Overall	3.02	0.637	Average Cultural Competence

As shown in Table 1, the *personal involvement* of the students has a mean score of 2.57 (± 0.597), indicating that the students have an average personal involvement with the indigenous people of Bukidnon. The students' *skills on culture* have a mean score of 3.03 (± 0.626), indicating that the students' skills regarding the culture of the indigenous people of Bukidnon is on an average level. The student's *knowledge on culture* has a mean score of 3.07 (± 0.582), indicating that the student knowledge on culture of the indigenous people of Bukidnon is also on an average level. The student *knowledge of cultural communities* has a mean score of 3.10 (± 0.539), indicating the students' knowledge of the cultural communities in Bukidnon is also on an average level. However, the student *awareness of culture* has a mean score of 3.31 (± 0.606), indicating the student's awareness regarding the indigenous people of Bukidnon is on a high level. Overall, the students have a mean score of 3.02 (± 0.637), indicating that the students have an average cultural competence.

Personal Involvement

Regarding the *personal involvement* of the student, there could be several reasons why college students have limited involvement with the indigenous people of Bukidnon. For instance, the remote location the different tribes of Bukidnon would be difficult for students to travel to and immerse themselves with the indigenous culture (Bakar, et al., 2014; Cornelio & Castro, 2016). Additionally, there may be few opportunities available for students to interact with the indigenous people of Bukidnon (Halualani, et al., 2004).

On that note, the limited involvement with the indigenous people of Bukidnon can impact the student cultural competence in several ways. Cultural competence refers to the ability to

understand, appreciate, and effectively interact with people from diverse cultural backgrounds (Guzman, et al., 2016; Grosser, 2020). By having limited exposure to the indigenous culture of Bukidnon, students may develop a narrow understanding of indigenous culture. Additionally, without firsthand experience, students may rely on secondhand information or textbooks that provide limited information about the nuances of the culture (Oliver, 2008; Curtis, et al, 2019).

Furthermore, students who have limited exposure to indigenous culture may develop stereotypes based on limited information, leading to incorrect assumptions and judgments about the culture (Caparoso & Collins, 2015). Moreover, cultural immersion allows students to broaden their perspectives and develop empathy and understanding for different cultures (Buchanan, et al., 2021). However, limited involvement with the indigenous people of Bukidnon may prevent students from experiencing personal growth (Doyle, Helms, & Westrup, 2004; Hipolito-Delgado, et al., 2013).

Skill on Culture

Regarding the student's *skill on culture*, it is possible that college have an average skill on culture regarding the indigenous people of Bukidnon because they may not have had previous exposure or education on this specific culture (Halualani, et al., 2004; Curtis, et al., 2019). They may also have limited access to resources such as books or experts who can provide them with more knowledge about the indigenous people of Bukidnon (Oliver, 2008). Additionally, their curriculum may not prioritize this specific culture or only give it limited attention (Palces, Abulencia, & Reyes, 2015; Vera Cruz, Madden, & Asante, 2018).

Having an average skill on culture regarding the indigenous people of Bukidnon can impact a student's cultural competence by limiting their understanding and appreciation for this group's unique beliefs, traditions, and practices (Curtis, et al., 2019). It can also impact their ability to effectively communicate and work with individuals from this culture in the future (Vecchio-Sadus, 2007). Students with higher levels of cultural competence are better able to adapt to different environments and understand and respect diverse perspectives, which are essential skills in today's increasingly globalized society (Van Laar, et al., 2017).

Knowledge on Culture

Regarding the students' *knowledge on culture*, students may have an average knowledge on culture regarding the indigenous people of Bukidnon because of several factors. Primarily, the course may have limited coverage of the specific culture of the Bukidnon indigenous people (Hipolito-Delgado, et al., 2013; Palces, Abulencia, & Reyes, 2015). Moreover, the students may not have had prior exposure or experience with the Bukidnon indigenous culture (Bakar, et al., 2014; Cornelio & Castro, 2016). Additionally, the students may have limited access to resources or references about the Bukidnon indigenous culture (Oliver, 2008).

Having an average knowledge on culture regarding the indigenous people of Bukidnon may impact the student's cultural competence in several ways. Accordingly, the student's understanding of the Bukidnon indigenous culture may be limited and incomplete, hindering their ability to communicate and connect with the indigenous community effectively (Vecchio-Sadus, 2007). Furthermore, the student may have biases and stereotypes about the Bukidnon indigenous culture, which may affect their behavior and attitudes towards the community (Caparoso &

Collins, 2015). Additionally, the student's cultural competence in dealing with diverse cultures may be limited, affecting their ability to navigate and engage in cross-cultural situations effectively (Tharp, 2017; Grosser, 2020).

Knowledge on Cultural Communities

Regarding the students' *knowledge on cultural communities*, students may have an average knowledge of cultural communities regarding the indigenous people of Bukidnon because of various factors. For instance, their background and exposure to the indigenous people's history, culture, and traditions before enrolling can significantly impact their level of understanding and knowledge (Halualani, et al., 2004; Bakar, et al., 2014; Cornelio & Castro, 2016). Moreover, the educational system's limited coverage and attention to indigenous people's studies in the Philippines may contribute to the lack of understanding and awareness of students enrolled in the mentioned course (Ty, 2010). Although the education system has made efforts to integrate indigenous people's studies into the curricula, it remains a challenge that requires more attention and resources (Palces, Abulencia, & Reyes, 2015; Drbohlav & Hejkrlik, 2017).

Having an average knowledge of cultural communities can impact a student's cultural competence in several ways. Students may lack the necessary cultural sensitivity to deal with particular issues or interact with indigenous communities effectively (Kawaguchi-Suzuki, et al., 2019). Additionally, it is imperative to expose students to a diverse range of resources, experiences, and perspectives that can broaden their cultural competence (Botelho & Lima, 2020). This can include engaging with indigenous communities, incorporating more in-depth analyses of indigenous people's issues and experiences, and promoting a positive attitude and appreciation towards cultural diversity (Hipolito-Delgado, et al., 2013; Buchanan, et al., 2021).

Awareness of Culture

Regarding the students' *awareness of culture*, students have a high awareness of the culture of the indigenous people of Bukidnon mainly because the course (Reading in Philippine History with Indigenous People Studies) is designed to provide them with in-depth knowledge and understanding of the culture, traditions, and customs of the indigenous people of the Philippines (Abad, 2020). The course focuses on the social, political, and economic history of the indigenous people of Bukidnon, their struggles, and issues, as well as their contributions to Philippine history (Improgo, 2012; Alic & Baul, 2021). The students are exposed to different literature, indigenous texts, and narratives that give them an appreciation of the indigenous people's way of life and worldview (Vecchio-Sadus, 2007; Vera Cruz, Madden, & Asante, 2018; Curtis, et al, 2019).

Having a high level of awareness of the culture of the indigenous people of Bukidnon can impact the student's cultural competence positively. Cultural competence refers to the ability to understand and appreciate people from different cultural backgrounds (Guzman, et al, 2016; Grosser, 2020). By having an awareness of the culture of the indigenous people, students are more likely to develop empathy and respect towards the indigenous community (Leung, Ang, & Tan, 2014; Botelho & Lima, 2020). Moreover, students with high cultural competence can easily interact and communicate with the indigenous people of Bukidnon and understand their perspectives, values, and beliefs. They can also avoid stereotyping, miscommunication, and cultural clashes, which are common in culturally diverse settings (Tharp, 2017; Curtis, et al., 2019).

Cultural Competence

Based on the results of Table 1, having an average level of cultural competence means that someone has a basic understanding and sensitivity to cultural differences but may still have room for improvement in their interactions and dealings with people from various cultures (Leung, Ang, & Tan, 2014; Arasaratnam, 2016). It is essential to strive for continuous learning and improvement to become more culturally competent in today's diverse and interconnected world (Guzman, et al., 2016; Tharp, 2017; Savicki, 2020).

Comparison the Components of Cultural Competence

Table 2 displays the comparison of the five (5) components of cultural competence of the students.

Table 2.

Comparison of the five components of cultural competence

Component	Mean	F	p
Awareness of Culture	3.31 a		
Knowledge of Cultural Communities	3.10 ab		
Knowledge on Culture	3.07 b	21.586	0.000**
Skills on Culture	3.03 b		
Personal Involvement	2.57 c		

NOTE: **-p<0.001

As presented in Table 2, the f-value of the five categories is 21.586 with a p-value of 0.000 (p<0.05), indicating that there is a significant difference between the five categories of cultural competence. Additionally, Table 2 illustrates that *awareness of culture* has a high level as compared to the other components. *Knowledge of cultural communities, culture, and skill on culture* has an average level. However, though *personal involvement* has an average level, it has differed from the other components according to the Tukey HSD test.

Students may have a high awareness to culture because they are exposed to a diverse range of cultures through their education and personal experiences. They may also be taught to acknowledge and respect cultural differences, which can increase their awareness (Improgo, 2012; Abad, 2020; Alic & Baul, 2021). Additionally, students may have a high awareness of culture because they are at an age and stage in their life where they are learning and exploring different cultures. They may be exposed to a diverse student population in their schools or universities, and through travel or social media (Tharp, 2017; Guzman, et al, 2016; Curtis, et al., 2019; Grosser, 2020 high awarenss).

Students may have a similar level of average knowledge and skills on culture and cultural communities due to the fact that the educational system or program they are enrolled in has a standardized curriculum that teaches these topics at a similar level to all students (Ty, 2010; Palces, Abulencia, & Reyes, 2015; Caparoso & Collins, 2015; Drbohlov & Hejkrlik, 2017). Additionally, most students at this level may have had similar experiences and exposures to these topics in their personal lives, which could also contribute to their similar levels of knowledge and skills (Bakar, et al., 2014; Cornelio & Castro, 2016; Buchanan, et al., 2021).

However, in general, students may have the lowest rating in personal involvement to culture because they may not have enough opportunities or exposure to engage with indigenous communities and their cultural practices (Halualani, et al., 2004; Doyle, Helms, & Westrup, 2004; Hipolito-Delgado, et al., 2013; Guzman, et al., 2016; Grosser, 2020). Moreover, the education system may focus more on Western culture and may not prioritize educating students about the histories and practices of indigenous communities. This may lead to a lack of understanding and appreciation for the diversity of cultures (Oliver, 2008; Caparoso & Collins, 2015; Vera Cruz, Madden, & Asante, 2018; Curtis, et al, 2019).

Nevertheless, it is important to note that cultural competence is a lifelong learning process, and individuals may have varying levels of competence in different areas (Guzman, et al., 2016; Botelho & Lima, 2020; Grosser, 2020). It is important to continue to learn and educate oneself on different cultures and to actively engage with diverse communities (Tharp, 2017; Savicki, 2020).

CONCLUSION

The following conclusions can be generated from the result of the study. The students have a generally positive level of interest, involvement, and knowledge about the indigenous people of Bukidnon and their culture. They also have a high level of awareness about the indigenous people's culture and communities. However, their level of cultural competency is only average. Nevertheless, the course in Reading in Philippine History with Indigenous People Studies is an excellent way to enhance the cultural competence of college students by providing them with knowledge and understanding of the indigenous people's culture and history, particularly the people of Bukidnon. Cultural competence is a valuable skill that can help students interact positively with people from different cultural backgrounds and add value to their personal and professional lives.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on these findings, it is recommended that further efforts could be made to increase the cultural competency of the participants. This can be achieved through additional education and training on the customs and values of the indigenous cultural communities of Bukidnon. Additional studies could be conducted to explore the relationship of cultural competence and academic achievement of student in the course Reading in Philippine History. Furthermore, the result suggests to foster more opportunities for interaction and dialogue with the indigenous communities to deepen the participants' understanding of their cultural practices and ways of life.

Moreover, it is important to continue promoting awareness of the indigenous people's culture and histories, particularly to the wider populace, in order to preserve and celebrate their heritage. Additionally, improving the student's knowledge and understanding of the Bukidnon indigenous cultural communities can help enhance their cultural competence and promote better engagement and appreciation of diverse cultures. Lastly, educators can provide opportunities for students to immerse themselves in the culture through field trips, community visits, and participation in cultural events.

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